

WHAT IS THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPITAL (PC) AND ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE (OJ) ON IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR IN LOCAL HOSPITAL, SOUTH SULAWESI

Monika Moan Mardhono ¹, Andi Indahwaty Sidin ², Syahrir Andi Pasinringi ³,
Noor Bahry Noer ⁴, Andi Zulkifli ⁵ and Fridawaty Rivai ⁶

¹ Candidate of Master in Hospital Administration Study Program, Faculty of Public Health, Hasanuddin University, Indonesia. Email: monikamoan@gmail.com, ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-7703-2974>

² Hospital Administration Study Program, Faculty of Public Health, Hasanuddin University, Indonesia, Hasanuddin University Hospital, Indonesia. Email: idhsidin@unhas.ac.id, ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9362-0780>

^{3,4,6} Hospital Administration Study Program, Faculty of Public Health, Hasanuddin University, Indonesia. Email: ³syahrir65@yahoo.com, ⁴noerbahrynoor@gmail.com, ⁶fridarivai@yahoo.com, ORCID ID: ³<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5947-2596>,

⁴<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9944-9478>, ⁶<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7336-7001>

⁵ Department of Epidemiology, Faculty of Public Health, Hasanuddin University, Indonesia. Email: zulkifliabdullah@yahoo.com, ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4437>

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11392620](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11392620)

Abstract

This study aims to analyse the effect of psychological capital and organizational justice on organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) in professionals at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province. This type of research is quantitative research, namely analytical observations using a cross sectional study design. This research was conducted at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province from March to May 2024. The population in this study were all professional staff at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province. The number of employees based on profession or type of staffing is 561 people. The sample using the slovin formula obtained 236 respondents. The statistical tests used were chi square test and multiple linear regression. The results showed that the psychological capital variable was in the good category (79.2%), and the organizational justice variable was in the high category (87.7%). There is an influence of the self efficacy dimension (p-value = 0.000), optimism dimension (p-value = 0.000), resilience dimension (p-value = 0.012), distributive justice (p-value = 0.000), interactional justice (p-value = 0.001). There is no effect of the hope dimension (p-value = 0.082), and procedural justice variables (p-value = 0.333) on organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) in the profession at Labuang Baji Hospital. The optimism dimension variable with the largest Exp (B) or OR (Odds Ratio) value = 17.967, so that variable is determined as the most influential factor simultaneously on organizational citizenship behaviour.

Keywords: *Psychological Capital, Organizational Justice, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Health Professions, Hospitals.*

INTRODUCTION

Organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) is very important in the work environment used for human resource management to improve the quality of personnel and services offered by the organisation [1]. Psychological capital (PsyCap) is a concept that refers to a number of positive psychological factors, including hope, optimism, self-efficacy, and resilience, that individuals have in the work environment [2]. A state of positive psychological development characterised by an individual's self-efficacy in their ability to strive for success in the face of challenging tasks, [3] make positive attribution by always identifying the best in every situation while expecting the best

outcome [4] perseverance towards a goal, ability to self-direct towards a goal towards success [5] and when beset by problems and difficulties, persevere and come back resilient and even go beyond to succeed [6]. Organisational justice is one of the antecedent factors that focus on individuals. Organizational justice is an individual's subjective perception of how they are treated fairly in the organisation, and whether this perception affects employee loyalty to the organisation [7]; [8]. Organizational justice is divided into three dimensions, namely: distributive justice (perception of allocation), procedural justice (perception of processes and rules in decision making), and interactional justice (interaction relationships within the organisation) [9]; [10]. Through these three dimensions, organisations can treat employees in a fair way so that employees tend to show their organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB). This positive behaviour of employees working beyond formal responsibilities (extra-role) is also called Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB). Therefore, an organisation's awareness of its employees' needs is important to maintain the quality of their work [11].

OCB reportedly supports innovation and development through addressing and fulfilling new hospital and patient demands [12]. High employee OCB behaviour reflects high employee commitment to the best performance so that the quality of service provided can exceed customer expectations [13]. High OCB is associated with quality service. However, the contribution of OCB to service quality has limited conceptual and empirical support [14].

Based on data analysis of the minimum service standards (SPM) in 2020 at Labuang Baji Hospital, which is based on the 2012 Minimum Service Standards Guidelines, it can be seen that there are several indicators in various services that do not meet the standards. Some of them are: in emergency services, emergency service providers who have STRs from KKI and SIPs and are certified (ATLS / BTLS / ACLS / PPGD / GELS) that are still valid do not meet the standard because the percentage achievement is only 60.95%. This may impact the quality of emergency care provided, and less motivated staff may not make the extra effort to ensure minimum service standards are met. In outpatient services, the indicator of outpatient waiting time does not meet the standard because at Labuang Baji Hospital it takes ≥ 60 minutes. Delays in outpatient waiting time and the availability of safety beds are factors that can affect patients' perceptions of service quality. When waiting time standards are not met (≥ 60 minutes), patients may feel unappreciated and service quality is affected. The specialist visit hours indicator also did not meet the standard as it only reached 82.3%. The quality of specialist visit hours and the incidence rate of postoperative infections not meeting the standard may also create patient dissatisfaction. Dissatisfied patients may be less likely to provide positive feedback or provide additional support to the hospital. Medical staff who see that their efforts in maintaining quality doctor visits or preventing postoperative infections are not appreciated may also be less motivated to behave proactively in support of the organisation. The incidence of postoperative infections also did not meet the standard as 1.68% of patients had infections. The high rate of postoperative infection reflects problems in the quality of postoperative care in the hospital. Patients who develop postoperative infections may face serious and high-risk complications. In such situations, it is important for the medical staff to provide extra care, intensive monitoring, and emotional support to the affected patients. Patient dissatisfaction due to high post-operative infections may hinder medical staff as they may be less motivated to provide the extra attention needed.

Based on the findings of the low achievement of 4 (four) SPM indicators at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province, it is interesting to investigate whether this is related to low psychological capital, organizational justice, and organizational citizenship behaviour in the profession at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province.

METHOD

This type of research is quantitative research, namely analytical observations using a cross-sectional study design. The research was conducted from March to May 2024. The population in this study were all professional staff at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province, totalling 561 people. The sample in this study was part of the professional staff at Labuang Baji Hospital using the Slovin formula, totalling 234 people. The analysis used is multiple linear regression. Data collection was carried out using a research instrument in the form of a questionnaire adopted from Indahwaty Sidin's research which had been tested for validity and reliability which showed that the questionnaire was valid and reliable so that it could be used.

RESULTS

The general characteristics of the respondents are the characteristics inherent in the respondents. The characteristics of the respondents shown include age, gender, education, length of work in the hospital, length of work in the unit, employment status, with the following characteristics:

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents Based on Respondent Characteristics at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province in 2024

No	Respondent Characteristics	n	%	Total	
1	Age	21-30 year		236	
		31-40 year	28		11.9
		41-50 year	90		38.1
		>50 yaer	88		37.3
		21-30 year	30		12.7
2	Education	High school/equivalent	14	5.9	236
		D3 / Equivalent	56	23.7	
		D4 / S1 / Equivalent	125	53.0	
		S2	39	16.5	
		S3	2	0.8	
3	Length of Service at Current Hospital	1-5 year	43	18.2	236
		6-10 year	52	22.0	
		11-15 year	70	29.7	
		16-20 year	42	17.8	
		21-25 year	13	5.5	
		≥26 year	16	6.8	
4	Employment Status	Civil Servants	165	69.9	236
		Non-civil servants	49	20.8	
		Contract/P3K	22	9.3	

Based on the table above, it is known that the characteristics of respondents based on age are mostly in the age group 31-40 years, namely 90 people (38.1%). The characteristics of respondents based on gender were mostly female respondents,

namely 206 people (87.3%). Characteristics of respondents based on the highest level of education are respondents with the last education D4 / S1 / equivalent, namely 125 people (53.0%). The characteristics of respondents based on length of work in the hospital were mostly respondents with a tenure of 11-15 years, namely 70 people (29.7%). As for the characteristics of respondents based on length of service in the current unit, the most respondents were respondents with a tenure of 1-5 years, namely 75 people (31.8%). The characteristics of respondents based on their employment status were mostly respondents as civil servants, namely 165 people (69.9%). The frequency distribution of the research variables of the psychological capital variable dimension can be seen in the following table:

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Psychological Capital Variable Dimensions at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province, 2024

No	Variables	High	%	Low	%
1	<i>Hope</i>	171	72,5	65	27,5
2	<i>Optimism</i>	152	64,4	84	35,6
3	<i>Resiliency</i>	121	51,3	115	48,7
4	<i>Self-Efficacy</i>	162	68,6	74	31,4
	Total	236	100,0	236	100,0

From the table above, it can be seen that the psychological capital variable for the dimension that has the highest percentage is the hope dimension of 72.5%.

The frequency distribution of organizational justice variable dimensions can be seen in the following table:

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Organizational Justice Variable Dimensions at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province in 2024

No	Variables	High	%	Low	%
1	<i>Distributive Justice</i>	134	56,8	102	43,2
2	<i>Procedural Justice</i>	170	72,0	66	28,0
3	<i>Interactional Justice</i>	200	84,7	36	15,3
	Total	236	100,0	236	100,0

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the organizational justice variable for the dimension that has the highest percentage is the interactional justice dimension of 84.7%.

The effect of psychological capital on organizational citizenship behaviour on professional staff at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province can be seen in the table below:

Table 4: The Effect of Psychological Capital on Organizational Citizenship Behaviour in Professional Personnel at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province in 2024

Variables	P-value	Description
Dimensions <i>self-efficacy</i> to <i>organizational citizenship behavior</i>	0,000	There is an influence of dimension <i>self-efficacy</i> to <i>organizational citizenship behavior</i>
Dimensions <i>optimism</i> to <i>organizational citizenship behavior</i>	0,000	There is an influence of dimension <i>optimism</i> to <i>organizational citizenship behavior</i>
Dimensions <i>hope</i> to <i>organizational citizenship behavior</i>	0,082	There is no effect of dimension <i>hope</i> to <i>organizational citizenship behavior</i>
Dimensions <i>resiliency</i> to <i>organizational citizenship behavior</i>	0,012	There is an influence of dimension <i>resiliency</i> to <i>organizational citizenship behavior</i>

Based on table 4, it can be seen that there is an effect of dimension *self-efficacy* (p-value = 0,000), dimension *optimism* (p-value = 0,000), and dimension *resiliency* (p-value = 0,012 to *organizational citizenship behavior*. Whereas in the dimension variable *hope* (p-value = 0,082) shows no effect on *organizational citizenship behavior*. This may be due to the overlapping of dimensions *optimism* and *hope* so that respondents could not distinguish between the two dimensions. According to Shaleh 2015, not all dimensions of the *psychological capital* which is valid in its measurement [15].

The effect of organizational justice on organizational citizenship behaviour on professional staff at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province can be seen in the table below:

Table 5: Organizational Justice on Organizational Citizenship Behavior in Professional Personnel at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province in 2024

Variables	p-value	Description
Distributive justice towards organizational citizenship behavior	0,004	There is an effect distributive justice towards organizational citizenship behavior
Procedural justice towards organizational citizenship behavior	0,333	There is an effect procedural justice towards organizational citizenship behavior
Interactional justice towards organizational citizenship behavior	0,001	There is an effect interactional justice towards organizational citizenship behavior

Based on table 5, it can be seen that there is an influence of distributive justice (p-value = 0.000), and interactional justice (p-value = 0.001), on organizational citizenship behaviour. Meanwhile, the procedural justice variable shows no effect (p-value = 0.333) on organizational citizenship behaviour. These results indicate that health professionals' perceptions of procedural justice in making compensation, promotion, job variety and feedback decisions do not have a significant impact on the formation of altruism and courtesy behaviours. This indicates that procedural justice perceived by health professionals does not have a direct impact on the formation of OCB, but is preceded by the formation of job satisfaction and organisational commitment.

The results of multiple logistic regression analysis of independent variables on organizational citizenship behaviour on professional staff at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province in 2024.

Table 6: Results of Logistic Regression Analysis of Independent Variables on Organizational Citizenship Behaviour in Professional Personnel at Labuang Baji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province in 2024

Variables	B	S.E.	Wald	Df	Exp(B)
Hope	-0,754	0,517	2,128	1	0,470
Optimism	2,889	0,480	36,208	1	17,967
Resiliency	1,487	0,476	9,756	1	4,424
Self Efficacy	1,910	0,434	19,409	1	6,752
Distributive Justive	0,901	0,437	4,258	1	2,462
Prosedural Justive	-0,343	0,508	0,457	1	0,709
Interactional Justice	1,211	0,547	4,896	1	3,358

Table 6 shows that after multivariate analysis using multiple logistic regression, the logistic regression coefficient value for the dimension variable is obtained *hope* (B_1) = -0,754, dimensions *optimism* (B_2) = 2,889, dimensions *resiliency* (B_3) = 1,487, dimensions *self-efficacy* (B_4) = 1,910, variables *distributive justice* (B_5) = 0,901,

variables *prosedural justive* (B_6) = -0,343, variables *interactional justice* (B_7) = 1,211. The p value of each variable, namely the dimension *hope* (p-value = 0,082), dimension *optimism* (p-value = 0,000), dimension *resiliency* (p-value = 0,012), dimension *self-efficacy* (p-value = 0,000), *distributive justice* (p-value = 0,000), *prosedural justice* (p-value = 0,333), and *interactional justice* (p-value = 0,001). By paying attention to the p value, it can be concluded that the optimism dimension variable with the largest Exp (B) or OR (Odds Ratio) value = 17.967, so that the variable is determined as the most influential factor simultaneously on organizational citizenship behaviour. This is because optimism is a strong learning in terms of self-discipline, analysis of past mistakes, and planning to prevent bad things from happening so that individuals with high optimism are able to feel the implications cognitively and emotionally when they get success [16].

DISCUSSION

The results showed that the psychological capital variable for the dimension that had the highest percentage was the hope dimension at 72.5% and for the lowest dimension, the resilience dimension, which was 51.3%. The frequency distribution for psychological capital variables is in the good category (79.2%). There is an influence of the self-efficacy dimension (p-value = 0.000), the optimism dimension (p-value = 0.000), and the resiliency dimension (p-value = 0.012) on organizational citizenship behaviour. While the variable dimension of hope (p-value = 0.082) shows no effect on organizational citizenship behaviour. This is in line with the results of Lather and Kaur's (2015) research which shows that psychological capital is a significant positive variable on organisational behaviour variables, because it can improve performance and development [17]. This is also in line with the results of research by Dadang, et al 2021 which show that psychological capital has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behaviour [18]. The results of research by Imam, et al 2015 show that psychological capital has a significant effect on OCB [19].

In an effort to increase organizational citizenship behaviour, one of them can be achieved through self-efficacy in employees [20]. Self-efficacy concerns a person's perception that any form of effort made can lead to success, and ultimately can increase the individual's ability to maintain efforts in achieving goals. Employees with high self-efficacy are more likely to show persistence and intensity in their approach to their job role and seek more challenging goals [21]. Self-efficacy influences an employee's assessment of a particular situation and any applicable rules or procedures and will therefore influence the employee's decisions and behaviour in the workplace [22]. Optimistic employees will not be easily disappointed by unpleasant experiences at work. Hopeful employees will be more motivated to be able to demonstrate performance that exceeds the company's minimum standards [23]. Resiliency will make employees more resilient in the face of failure at work so that it does not easily make them give up. Employees will try to find innovations and new ways of working that can overcome these failures [24].

The organizational justice variable for the dimension that has the highest percentage is the interactional justice dimension of 84.7% and for the lowest dimension, the distributive justice dimension, which is 56.8%. The frequency distribution for organizational justice variables is in the high category (87.7%). The variable of distributive justice (p-value = 0.000), and interactional justice (p-value = 0.001), shows that there is an influence on organizational citizenship behavior. Meanwhile, the

procedural justice variable shows no effect (p-value = 0.333) on organizational citizenship behaviour. This is also in line with the results of Raisa's research, Rojuaniah 2023 which shows that organizational justice has a positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior [25]. The results of research by Ashari, et al 2019 shows the findings of this study are organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on employee OCB [26].

In every company, organizational justice has a very important role for the sense of fairness experienced by employees. There are three dimensions of fairness that are focused here, namely distributive justice which focuses on ways to compensate employees. The compensation referred to here is related to the wages/salaries received by employees or other bonuses whose amount certainly adjusts the performance of these employees [27]. The second is procedural justice which focuses on how to make decisions on a problem that can have an impact on the sense of injustice in the minds of employees, especially if at the time of decision making, employees do not have room for disagreement. The third is interactional justice which refers to the interaction of employees with other employees and with their superiors where respect and mutual appreciation are more emphasised in shaping justice. These three dimensions of organizational justice have an impact on whether or not employees are satisfied at work [28].

The optimism dimension variable with the largest Exp (B) or OR (Odds Ratio) value = 17.967, so that variable is determined as the most influential factor simultaneously on organizational citizenship behaviour.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that: The psychological capital variable shows that there is an influence of the dimensions of self-efficacy (p-value = 0.000), optimism (p-value = 0.000), and resilience (p-value = 0.012) on organizational citizenship behavior in the profession at Labuang Baji Hospital. Organizational justice variables show there is an influence of distributive justice (p-value = 0.000), and interactional justice (p-value = 0.001), on organizational citizenship behaviour in the profession at Labuang Baji Hospital. There is no effect of the hope dimension (p-value = 0.082), and procedural justice (p-value = 0.333) on organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) in the profession at Labuang Baji Hospital. The optimism dimension with the largest Exp (B) or OR (Odds Ratio) value = 17.967, so that the variable is determined as the most influential factor simultaneously on organizational citizenship behaviour. Suggestions, namely for further research, can be developed with other dimensional variables. In addition, employees who are able to show performance need to be given a fairer and more equitable award in allocating awards to each employee.

References

- 1) [Banwo, A.O., & Du J. When the good outweighs the bad: Organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) in the workplace. *Human Resource Development International*, 23(1), 88–97. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13678868.2018.1449546>. 2020;
- 2) Lorenz, T., Beer, C., Pütz, J., & Heinitz K. Measuring psychological capital: Construction and validation of the Compound PsyCap Scale (CPC-12). *PLoS ONE*, 11(4), Artic e0152892 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone0152892>. 2016;
- 3) Bandura A. Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*, 84(2), 191–215. 1977.

- 4) Jitendra, M., Jenny, S., Brian, L., & Bharat M. Optimism and longevity. *Advances in Management*, 3(3), 50–62. 2010.
- 5) Snyder CR. Hypothesis: There is hope. In C. R. Snyder (Ed.), *Handbook of hope: Theory, measures, and applications* (pp. 3–21). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-012654050-5/50003-8>. 2000;
- 6) Masten, A. S., & Reed MGJ. Resilience in development. In C. R. Snyder & S. J. Lopez (Eds.), *Handbook of positive psychology* (pp. 74–88). Oxford University Press. 2002;
- 7) Nandan, Tamizarasu., and Abdul MMA. Organizational Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behavior: Mediating Role of Psychological Capital. *Am Int J Soc Sci* 4(6)148-156. 2015;
- 8) Mahendra, i made dika and Surya ida bagus ketut. Pengaruh Iklim Organisasi, Motivasi Kerja Dan Keadilan Organisasi Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)', 6(9), pp. 4659–4688. 2017;
- 9) Moorman RH. Relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behaviors: Do fairness perceptions influence employee citizenship? *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 76(6), 845-855. 1991;
- 10) Cropanzano, R. and Molina A. Organizational Justice', *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences: Second Edition*, (December 2015), pp. 379–384. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-08-097086- 8.22033-3. 2015;
- 11) Awang, R., Mohd, W. and Wan R. The Impact of Organizational Justice on Organizational citizenship behavior in Malaysian Higher Education', 6(5), pp. 674–678. doi: 10.5901/mjss.2015.v6n5s2p674. 2015;
- 12) Khaola R. The effects of transformational leadership on organisational citizenship behaviour: the role of organisational justice and affective commitment. *Manag Res Rev*. 2020;
- 13) Panagiotis D. The effects of high performance work systems in employees' service-oriented OCB. *Int J Hosp Manag*. 2020;
- 14) Sidin, Arifah M. Organizational climate enhance service quality through enhancing OCB in public hospital. *Biomed Res*. 2019;
- 15) Shaleh A. Analisis Faktor Konfirmatorik Skala Modal Psikologis. Embracing A New Way Of Life : Positive Psychology For Better A Mental Health. *Seminar Nasional Positive Psychologi*. 2015;
- 16) Luthans, F., Avolio, B. J., Avey, J. B., & Norman S, M. Positive psychological capital: Measurement and relationship with performance and satisfaction. *Personnel Psychology*, 60(3), 541–572. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.2007.00083.x>. 2007;
- 17) Prof. Anu Singh Lather, Ms. Simran Kaur. Psychological Capital as Predictor of Organizational Commitment and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *Int J Indian Psychol*. 2015;2(4).
- 18) Sudirno D, Sri Mulyani H, Prihartini E. Psychological Capital Dan Komitmen Organisasional Pengaruhnya Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Ocb) Pada Karyawan Pt. Bpr Majalengka Jabar. *J Co Manag*. 2022;4(2):648–58.
- 19) Imam D. Intervensi organizational citizenship behavior untuk akselerasi pembelajaran di PT Pembangkit Listrik ABC = Organizational citizenship behavior intervention for accelerating the learning in PT Pembangkit Listrik ABC. URI <https://lib.ui.ac.id/m/detail.jsp?id=20414959&lokasi=lokal>. 2015;
- 20) Dani Saadi S. Pengaruh self-efficacy terhadap work performance dan organizational citizenship behavior melalui job crafting. *Forum Ekon [Internet]*. 2021;23(2):318–30. Available from: <http://journal.feb.unmul.ac.id/index.php/FORUMEKONOMI>
- 21) Carter, W. R., Nesbit, P. L., Badham, R. J., Parker, S. K., & Sung LK. The effects of employee engagement and self-efficacy on job performance: a longitudinal field study. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*. 29(17), 2483–2502 <https://doi.org/101080/0958519220161244096>. 2018;

- 22) Cohen, A., & Abedallah M. The mediating role of burnout on the relationship of emotional intelligence and self-efficacy with ocb and performance. *Manag Res Rev* 38(1), 2–28 <https://doi.org/101108/MRR-10-2013-0238>. 2015;
- 23) Dina. Pengaruh Modal Psikologis, Budaya Organisasi Dan Spiritualitas Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior. 2020;5(1):396–403.
- 24) Francisca H. Hubungan Antara Psychological Capital Dengan Organizational Citizenship Behavior Pada Karyawan PT. PLN (Persero) Distribusi Jawa Tengah Dan Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta. 2010;0–9.
- 25) Raisa NF, Rojuaniah R. Transformational Leadership and Organizational Justice Effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Organizational Commitment of Employees in the Industry XYZ. *J Bus Econ Res*. 2023;4(2):124–8.
- 26) Ashari I, Rahmat R, Allorante AI, Ahmad B. Effect of Organizational Justice on Organizational Citizenship Behaviour at Barombong Maritime Polytechnic Makassar City. 2019;4(11). Available from: [https://ijisrt.com/assets/upload/files/IJISRT19NOV423_\(2\).pdf](https://ijisrt.com/assets/upload/files/IJISRT19NOV423_(2).pdf)
- 27) Robbins, S. P. & Judge TAO. *rganizational Behaviour (15thed.)*. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Prentice hall. 2013;
- 28) Wijaya Y. Analisis Pengaruh Distributive Justice, Procedural Justice, Dan Interactional Justice Terhadap Jobsatisfaction Dan Organizational Citizenship Behavior Pada Divisi Produksi Dan Hrd Pt Kievit Indonesia Di Salatiga. *Agora*. 2019;7(1).